

RUNNING HEAD: Y2K AND PROFESSIONALISM

Tonight we're gonna program like it's 1999: The art of bringing civilization to its knees

Abstract

I examine the reasons given by contemporaries for the inclusion of the Y2K problem in COBOL, and the extension of those reasons into a split in the computer programming profession between those who view software development as an art and those who view it as engineering. This account extends research into the development of professional identity through intraprofessional argumentation.

Hasian, Condit & Lucaites found reason to be more optimistic than Critical Legal Studies scholars, no difficult task, in their observation that relationships brought into being by the legal system "possess a certain cultural authenticity insofar as they are forged in the fires of controversy where prudential concerns often necessitate the acceptance of less than perfect public arrangements" (1996, p. 327). The same might be said, and is in fact a good starting point for saying things about the transformation of a professional identity: when its practitioners disagree about how their work, their knowledge, and their constitutive principles are properly understood, then the negotiated outcome may *incorporate* difference, rather than fracturing along the fault line of that difference. Doctors, lawyers and clergy have confronted such re-founding moments again and again, but for younger professions that are the product of more recent inventions, there is less institutional history, a more shallow assemblage of precedent and reassuring history, to absorb the shock of such radical breaks and recombinations. A number of scholars have taken up the role argument plays in the construction of *identity*, from Douglas Ehninger's (1970) observation that argument understood as a method of mutual correction and refinement of knowledge puts all arguers' identities at risk, to Hazen & Williams' collection of essays (1997) addressing the interplay between argument and ethnic or national identity. Srader (2003, 2005, 2006) investigates the ways *professionals* argue among themselves, and how such argument shapes the *professional* identity, as well as how the identity constrains the available stock of arguments that can be made. And in the twilight years of the twentieth century, a professional field that had exploded into importance as the internet and other uses of the computer revolutionized work, play and governance, confronted a traumatic moment of contradiction that brought one such identity controversy into sharp relief. The lingering questions following the event have yet to be laid to rest, and disagreement over the identity persists, but the

question is now out in the open, and the potential for the adoption of a negotiated replacement identity has been enhanced.

"Never has a calamity been so predictable, and so inevitable, tied to a deadline that can be neither appealed nor postponed. Diplomacy is fruitless. Nuclear deterrence isn't a factor. This can't be filibustered into the next Congress" (Weingarten, 1999, p. F1). By the closing months of 1999, everyone who used a computer or had the potential to be affected indirectly by computer use was putting the finishing touches on contingency plans for the first day of the year 2000. If frantic repair efforts were successful, then the Y2K bug might not bring civilization to its knees. If, however, a single safety-critical system wasn't adequately re-tooled for the unforeseen hazard of one day becoming the next, then all manner of disasters might occur, from airplane crashes, to bank failures, to elevator malfunctions, to electricity, water and natural gas shutdowns. Public transportation might stop, hospital equipment malfunction, and the supply chain for manufacturing and consumer goods grind to a halt (Regan, 1998; Shahin, 1999). Because of the existence of a fail-deadly automated system that controlled Russian ICBMs, it seemed to some analysts a distinct possibility that a system-wide computer malfunction might trigger a full scale nuclear first strike (Donnelly, 1999).

In the event, very little happened; the predicted catastrophes fizzled. A few buses printed the wrong date on transfers. One video store nabbed a patron for returning a video which its records showed had been rented in 1900, and charged the poor delinquent over ninety-two thousand dollars in fines. "But considering the breadth and scope of computer usage worldwide, these early return failures [were] the proverbial pimple on a pumpkin" (Glass, 2000, p. 17).

As the dust settled, one question overtook another. In the months, weeks, hours, leading up to midnight, the dominant question had been "What can we do to protect ourselves from these

possibly disastrous outcomes?" When they failed to eventuate, another question many had asked, but largely deferred, took on added salience: "How did this happen?" How did presumably intelligent computer programmers design such a disastrous problem into their systems, and why didn't they catch it at an earlier stage, when fixing it might have been a smaller scale problem? Finally, even though this particular lapse had turned out not to pose the threat many had feared, was there the possibility of a sequel? Could we expect similar dilemmas that seemed inherent in the designed architecture of the network of computers upon which we had come to depend? Leon Kappelman, an information systems professor and leading Y2K commentator, explained that the real question wasn't about the reliability of the machinery, but about the routines adopted by the machinists: "Let's face it. Good intentions aside, computing professionals created the Y2K problem. Notwithstanding varying degrees of complicity by engineers, auditors, accountants, users, management, and others, the simple fact is that the code is broken and the code is the responsibility of the computing profession" (1999a, p. 23).

Those professionals, the ones best equipped to answer the lingering questions, did not cooperate in reassuring their shaken clients, either before or after zero-second. "Will the world melt down at midnight on Jan. 1, 2000, or will everything be just fine? No one knows. Y2K gurus, like professional economists, disagree about almost everything. For every 'expert' assuring us the computers of the world are ready, there's another one telling us to build bomb shelters and lay in stores of beef jerky and bottled water" (McMurry, 1999, p. 43). A similarly splintered heap of answers emerged to the questions of how this error had slipped through all safeguards, and what lessons had been learned about how computers operated and what made their operators tick.

Technical and practical roots of the Y2K bug

Called before Congressional hearings on the state of the economy, Alan Greenspan made a startling admission that went to the root of how the Y2K problem came to be:

I'm one of the culprits who created this problem. I used to write those programs back in the '60s and '70s... (laughter) ... and was so proud of the fact that I was able to squeeze a few elements of space out of my program by not having to put 19 before the year. And back then it was very important. We used to spend a lot of time running through various mathematical exercises before we started to write our programs so that they could be very clearly delimited with respect to space and the use of capacity. It never entered our minds that those programs would have lasted more than a few years. And as a consequence, they are very poorly documented. If I were to go back and look at some of the programs I wrote 30 years ago, I mean, I would have one terribly difficult time working my way through step by step. And to try to infer how one reads a program, when there are lots of alternate ways of doing things and all you've got is the code in front of you, is not simple (D'Amato, 1998, ¶¶ 292-295).

The principle constraints included severe limitations on storage media and a belief in the speed of innovation and resulting evanescence of code that turned out to be disastrously mistaken. One chronicler of the mistake explained it in these terms: "Imagine you own a car that gets one mile to the gallon, and every additional ounce in the passenger compartment further reduces the gas efficiency. You would do anything you could to lighten your load. You might even drive naked, gawkers be damned" (Weingarten, 1999, p. F1). Following a detailed list of limitations in technology that was considered state of the art at the time, he concludes, "Many programmers say today that they knew they were being sloppy. But there were greater priorities. So they drove naked" (p. F1). Furthermore, their belief in the brief lifespan of their work obscured the

possibility that the programming shortcut was likely to create difficulties. One programmer asking his manager about possible problems down the road; he recalled that the manager replied, "There's no way that we'll be using these programs twenty years from now" (Ackerman, 1998, ¶ 3).

Those two limitations, disk space and foresight, were compounded by other quirks and irregularities in the practice of software development. Robert Bemer, inventor of the ESC key, one of the authors of the COBOL programming language, and one of the most-sought Y2K consultants in the waning months of 1999, remembers telling his bosses at General Electric as early as 1969 that it was incredibly important that programmers implement four-digit years. Their reply, according to Bemer: "But if our already criticized industry tries to cram this standard down every assistant's personal life, we are going to create adverse reflections on our computer industry. I urge you not to take the stand you're reported" (O'Brien, 1999, ¶¶ 45-47). At the same time, Harry White, who worked for the Department of Defense and specialized in data elements, tried to bring the problem to his employers' attention. White explains, "The light went on for me in the early 1960s. I could see many applications by necessity needed a four-digit year. Personnel, medical records, retirement. When you do those with two digits, it will cause considerable problems. . . . I was not too popular back then" (Kesterton, 1998, p. A14). Unfortunately, White recounts the Department of Defense's disinterest in the problem, because "Defense had bigger worries. We were neck deep in Vietnam" (Weingarten, 1999, p. F1). White and Bemer joined forces to assemble a coalition of eighty six technical societies, who petitioned President Nixon to proclaim 1970 the Year of the Computer and urge programmers to root out shortcuts such as the two-digit year. Bemer recalls, "President Nixon refused to sign it because he was rather suspicious of computers, and so it never occurred" (Redmond, 1998, p. 12).

Outside pressure might not have been necessary if programmers themselves had succeeded in marshaling the will to correct the problem, but they were an iconoclastic bunch and not focused on imposing a collective discipline across the membership of their occupation. Bemmer reports that the natural language commands in COBOL lowered the barriers to entry to programming, by truncating the volume of learning required to craft programs that would operate properly. Unfortunately, the outcome was not necessarily good for the industry. "I thought it would open up a tremendous source of energy. It did. But what we got was arson" (Weingarten, 1999, p. F1). Pointing out the absence of training, licensure or safeguards, he concludes, "What can I say? We're a lousy profession" (p. F1). This vacuum of standards sowed the seeds of the Y2K problem by permitting programmers to implement their own varied date formats, such that a single approach to correcting the date couldn't account for all the variation. One programmer explains, "programmers are individuals and may not use the standard words for year such as date, or abbreviations such as yr, yy, yymmdd, mmdyy, etc., in their programs. In one case we found a programmer used the name SHIRLEY (his 'date' at the time) to represent dates in his program" (Burgess, 1998, ¶ 1). The programmers expect a certain degree of creativity and freedom from discipline and standardization, which may, unfortunately, hinder efforts to contain mistakes before their effects spread beyond any single programmer's control: "Programmers sometimes consider themselves as creative as novelists; to them, standards experts are squinty-eyed, pencil-necked editors--necessary, perhaps, but nit-picky and annoying. In this insular world, all debates are about small things; so small things can become very large" (Weingarten, 1999, p. F1). Tani Haque, president and founder of SQL software, sums up the anarchic spirit of many software developers in what are, for many industry commentators, fighting words: "When we manufacture a car, there's a whole process. In software, that process is still not that well-

known. It's still an art form" (Belsie, 1995, p. 9). Leon Kappelman does not disagree, but seizes upon the explanation as the target for his criticism and assignment of responsibility for the Y2K problem:

The "software is an art form" theory is just an excuse for the poor workmanship and shoddy products which have lead to debacles like this Y2K mess. Software is no more an art form than good architecture, or good medicine, or good scientific research are art forms -- They all have their creative side, but they're also rigorously disciplined endeavors. So too is good software development (Kappelman, 1999c, ¶ 10).

Software: Art form, science, or engineering?

Kappelman did not mince words when he addressed the House Judiciary Committee on the Y2K problem in 1999: "If software is an art form, then we have bet our future economic well being, perhaps our very survival, on this art form - Certainly we are not that foolish or frivolous" (Kappelman, 1999c, ¶ 10). He was not alone in his thinking. Forty years before his heated testimony, the editors of the *Communications of the ACM* editorialized, "If computer programming is to become an important part of computer research and development, a transition of programming from an art to a disciplined science must be effected" (Bauer, Juncosa & Perlis, 1959, p. 121). Victor R. Basili, a professor of computer science at the University of Maryland similarly complained that software development "needs to become more of an engineering discipline. It's treated too often as an art form, still" (Pollack, 1991, p. 39). Other commentators backed away from the blanketed condemnation, but insisted that "In safety-critical applications we must reject the 'software-as-art-form' approach. Programs and documentation must conform to standards that allow reviewers to feel confident they understand the software and can predict

how it will function in situations where safety depends on it" (Parnas, van Schouwen & Kwan, 1990, p. 640).

These insistent voices did not, however, represent a consensus. Equally firm opinion backed the position that software development *was* an art, rather than a species of engineering, and that such a perspective was both inevitable and appropriate. Donald Knuth, author of a seminal set of textbooks on programming entitled *The Art of Computer Programming* (1973), won the Association for Computing Machinery's Turing award for the text and other achievements; in his acceptance lecture, "Computer Programming as an Art" (1974), he not only defended his perspective, but offered a telling glimpse into the pattern of thinking that contributed to the Y2K problem:

One rather curious thing I've noticed about aesthetic satisfaction is that our pleasure is significantly enhanced when we accomplish something with limited tools. For example, the program of which I personally am most pleased and proud is a compiler I once wrote for a primitive minicomputer which had only 4096 words of memory, 16 bits per word. It makes a person feel like a real virtuoso to achieve something under such severe restrictions (p. 671).

Perhaps for many COBOL programmers, the omission of the first two digits was not only a concession to limitations, but also a pleasingly minimalist choice that served a streamlining purpose motivated not merely by necessity, but by aesthetics as well.

Knuth is not lacking allies that defend the art form perspective. Arny Epstein, a Harvard astrophysicist who changed careers to become a software developer for Lotus, explained, "It's an art form for me. I can just walk up to the computer and it's a lump of clay. I can make it do whatever I want it to" (Richards, 1990, p. A1). Charles Wang, founder and chairman of New

York software firm Computer Associates, similarly insists that "Producing great software isn't engineering, it's an art form. I find that musicians and philosophy students often make the best programmers" (Markoff, 1990, p. 29). Parnas, van Schouwen & Kwan admit that the view is widespread: "Traditionally, engineers have approached software as if it were an art form. Each programmer has been allowed to have his own style. Criticisms of software structure, clarity, and documentation were dismissed as 'matters of taste'" (1990, p. 639). Catching mistakes, in particular, is a task that software developers often categorize as art: "I have found good testers have a 'nose' for testing. They experience a kind of intuition that tells them what to test and how" (Armour, 2005, p. 17).

Others argue with equal fervor that software development ought to be considered a species of engineering. "If a bridge falls down, its designer can be sued for damages. A similar standard of professional liability should apply to the authors of computer programs, if lives or property are endangered by their failure" (Harvey, 1991, p. 27). Parnas goes so far as to blow the whistle on his fellow professionals:

When discussing the risks of using computers, we rarely mention the most basic problem: most programmers are not well educated for the work they do. Many have never learned the basic principles of software design and validation. Detailed knowledge of arcane system interfaces and languages is no substitute for knowing how to apply fundamental design principles. The year-2000 problem illustrates my point. Since the late 1960s, we have known how to design programs so that it's easy to change the amount of storage used for dates. Nonetheless, thousands of programmers wrote millions of lines of code that violated well-accepted design principles. The simplest explanation: those who designed and approved that software were incompetent (Parnas, 1997, p. 128)!

This stand-off between irreconcilable perspectives on the proper understanding of what it means to be a computer programmer is not an exercise in trivia. Major developments in the occupational field's evolution as a profession hang in the balance. Manion & Evan explain,

There are two opposing views as to whether computer programmers should be required to submit to a licensing procedure. One side states that the licensing of computer professionals is one way to achieve a heightened sense of accountability, responsibility, and knowledge in software development. The other side states that governmental regulation should not get involved because it will stifle the creativity and innovation that computer programmers are known for. (2000, p. 382)

Discussion

The struggle between fellow programmers to characterize the work, and therefore the profile of someone who did the work properly, highlighted two particular issues that developed along a trajectory unique to this profession: the *enjoyment* of work, and the *indeterminacy* of right answers. Fine reports detecting these two patterns in his study of chefs: "The rhetoric of art recognizes the unique standing of the object, coupled with an aesthetic sensibility of the worker" (1996, p. 104). For programmers, the divide seemed to track the gap between spontaneity and assurance, between construction and improvisation, between the fugue and the jazz solo.

Enjoyment of the work is certainly not a value that only programmers embrace, but some demand more immediate gratification than is expected in other fields. Professionals of every stripe report that they find their work meaningful. Doctors speak of the joy of saving lives, and lawyers collect tales of helping the powerless fend off the powerful. But computer programmers who tilt toward the "art form" position are far more likely to report that thinking of programming as art is a necessary prerequisite to their pleasure *in the moment*. Nearly every profession has

among its components a high density of tasks that might be characterized as drudgery: doctors must follow exacting protocols that may include very fussy calibration or mind-numbing repetition, lawyers must proceed step by detailed step through mountains of paperwork, and other professionals have their own scutwork. Even though some of the inglorious labor may be farmed out to assistants or apprentice proto-professionals, it seems almost inherent in the mystique of highly specialized work that cannot be carried out by the laity that some tasks will be effort- and attention-intensive, and thus have the potential to be unpleasant. The biggest reward, therefore, comes in the *culmination* of the labor. The notion, widespread among programmers, that a high priority ought to be making the actual *process* of programming an enjoyable one is a different emphasis. Knuth argues that "A programmer who subconsciously views himself as an artist will enjoy what he does and will do it better" (1974, p. 673).

Interestingly, Weiss offers an alternate perspective, asserting that the *principle-driven* end of the enterprise is the source of enjoyment, and the intuitive, artistic end is the more frustrating phase: "Design is the fun part of programming, but debugging is the painful part. In debugging, we essentially find the underlying mistakes and assumptions that turned our beautiful free-flowing code into a stagnant swamp. Today, debugging remains an art form, one not changed much over time (Weiss, 2001, ¶¶ 4-5). Thus, even within the argument sets, different programmers struggle over how the character of the work is best understood.

The second departure computer programmers routinely pursue from the typical set of claims made by a field on the professionalizing path is the indeterminacy of right answers. It is not uncommon for professionals to warn their clients that they can't guarantee an outcome, because disease, or a jury, do not follow predictable routines in every case. However, it is far more uncommon for professionals to admit that they can't tell work done properly from work

done *improperly*, that they may not be equipped with the knowledge to judge the quality of the practice. This claim has its adherents in the software development field. Knight and Leveson (2002) explain,

Different software systems and applications, however, require different techniques and knowledge. Although an IEEE committee has been trying to codify the material they consider essential for the successful practice of software engineering, they have explicitly excluded special needs and knowledge required for safety-critical software and systems, such as the skills and techniques necessary for designing and building real-time software. Relatively little scientific evaluation of software engineering techniques has been done, and it will be difficult to get consensus on what should be included and what should be excluded (2002, p. 89).

For arguers defending the "art form" perspective, the indeterminacy of a right way to program a computer was an immovable obstacle, and therefore something to be worked around.

Programmers could rely on trial and error, flashes of inspiration, eclectic methods and eccentricity to produce makeshift solutions that neither followed nor established principles that other programmers might agree upon. Arguers proceeding from the engineering perspective countered that the dearth of collective knowledge of principles that distinguished good software from bad software was not a permanent condition, that standardization and process construction were not death-blows to creativity, but rather safeguards against repeating mistakes and reinventing wheels. Their position matched far more closely the typical arguments made by gatekeepers in other professions, and made a stronger foundation for pursuing the claim that noninitiates outside the profession could not produce work that was trustworthy.

Conclusion

The parties on both sides of the divide may be guilty of asking the wrong question. Sociologist Gary Fine, in his inquiry into the rhetoric of professions, explains that "For those occupations that do not come to these identities naturally (i.e. through public consensus), a process of analogizing one's work to other realms is often necessary. If the pattern of one's work can be analogized to work of a higher status, some status may rub off" (1996, p. 112). With the indelible imprint computer usage is making on the everyday lives of the lion's share of the human race, it may be that programmers have reached a level of public awareness and acceptance that permits them to move out from under the shadow of artists and engineers, and take up their own identity. Many software developers have offered up approaches that obviate the question, either by rejecting both labels or suggesting a balance between the two. Squires complains that the art/science dilemma within a profession is an impoverished perspective: "While one can thus see why people have tried to understand the professions in terms of art and science, neither term seems adequate and there is no reason to think that marrying the two will make matters better rather than worse" (2005, p. 130). Harvey offers hope that a useful understanding of the work can be derived from *each*, that the fracture in mid-identity can be healed through incorporation of the useful inputs and disciplines of *both* fields of practice:

I have not suggested abandoning concerns about professional liability, conservative design, and teamwork in the context of programming projects in which lives or property are at risk. Rather, I have argued that software engineering concerns should be balanced by a lively sense of the artistic, creative side of professional programming, and that large ideas should come before technical details in the curriculum (Harvey, 1991, p. 28).

Marty Fahey, Arny Epstein's manager at Lotus, summarizes it this way: "You've got to have some structure ... but you also have to allow them to do great things. You have to keep the magic in the process" (Richards, 1990, p. A1).

The contested occupational identity of software developers has not yet reached a resolution. The ACM opposes licensure, pleading that "a software engineering license would be interpreted as an authoritative statement that the licensed engineer is capable of producing software systems of consistent reliability, dependability, and usability. The ACM Council concluded that our state of knowledge and practice is too immature to give such assurance" (White & Simons, 2002, p. 91). The legal system similarly keeps the professional status of computer programming unfocused and unsettled, although programmers might be forgiven for appreciating the form their vote of no confidence has taken:

...courts have consistently rejected attempts to sue software engineers and to make them liable for software-related malpractice. In explaining their decisions, courts note that malpractice (professional negligence) involves harm caused by the failure of a person to perform within the standards of his or her profession. Software engineering is not a licensed profession, they say, and therefore software engineers are not subject to malpractice (Knight & Leveson, 2002, p. 90).

And the tension between art and engineering at the heart of the industry continues to create issues. The systems for recording dates in C and Unix will cease functioning in 2038, windowing systems adopted to address the Y2K problem will outrun their usefulness between 2015 and 2050, and Microsoft products may experience date-related problems between 2019 and 2078 (Jones, 2000). Those dates now seem comfortably far off, but given the past track record of collective will to fix diffuse errors, that comfort might be misplaced. And at this writing, a new

bug affecting calendar-driven computer applications has been announced, and may cause a cascade of unexpected problems, all because of a change in the reckoning of daylight savings time (Waters, 2007). David Thewlis, director of CalConnect, a technology consortium that develops calendar and scheduling software, was asked to comment on the newly discovered glitch. He explained, "There's no rule that says you have to represent time in a certain way if you write a program" (Bergstein, 2007, ¶ 11). In other words, for many, it's still an art and not a science. And as Andy Warhol once said, "Art is what you can get away with."

References

- Ackerman, J. M. (1998, July 23). Prepared statement of Joel M. Ackerman, executive director, RX2000 Solutions Institute, before the Senate Special Committee on the Year 2000 Technology Problem. *Federal News Service*, Retrieved January 30, 2007, from the Lexis Academic Universe Database.
- Armour, P. G. (2005). The unconscious art of software testing. *Communications of the ACM*, 48, 15-18.
- Bauer, W. F., Juncosa, M. L., & Perlis, A. J. (1959). ACM publication policies and plans. *Communications of the ACM*, 6, 121-122.
- Belsie, L. (1995). Complexity of software hampers efforts to bridge the glitch gap. *Christian Science Monitor*, 9.
- Bergstein, B. (2007, February 14). A mini, minor Y2K: Earlier daylight-saving time could foil computer calendars. *The Associated Press State & Local Wire*. Retrieved February 14, 2007, from the Lexis Academic Universe database.
- D'Amato, A. (1998, February 25.) Holds hearing on the state of the U.S. economy. *FDCH Political Transcripts*, Retrieved February 5, 2007, from the Lexis Academic Universe Database.
- Donnelly, J. (1999, November 21). Y2K long shot: US-Russian nuclear war. *Boston Globe*, A1.
- Ehninger, D. (1970). Argument as method: Its nature, its limitations, and its uses. *Speech Monographs*, 37 (2), 101-110.
- Fine, G. A. (1996). Justifying work: Occupational rhetorics as resources in restaurant kitchens. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 41, 90-115.

- Harvey, B. (1991, February). Symbolic programming vs. the A.P. curriculum. *The Computing Teacher*, 27-29.
- Hasian, M., Condit, C. M., & Lucaites, J. L. (1996). The rhetorical boundaries of 'the law': A consideration of the rhetorical culture of legal practice and the case of the 'separate but equal' doctrine. *Quarterly Journal of Speech*, 82, 323-342.
- Hazen, M.D., & Williams, D.C. (1997, Fall). Introduction: Argument and identity. *Argumentation and advocacy*, 34 (3), v-viii.
- Jones, C. (2000, December 31). Remember Y2K? Other software dangers are on the horizon. *San Diego Union-Tribune*, G1.
- Kappelman, L. (1999). Saving our sacred honor. *Communications of the ACM*, 42, 23-26.
- Kesterton, M. (1998, October 12). Chaos: Whom to blame. *The Globe and Mail*, A14.
- Knight, J. C., & Leveson, N. G. (2002). Should software engineers be licensed? *Communications of the ACM*, 45, 87-90.
- Knuth, D. E. (1973). *The art of computer programming*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley Publishing Company.
- Knuth, D. E. (1974). Computer programming as an art. *Communications of the ACM*, 17, 667-673.
- Markoff, J. (1990, May 20). Software offers solid future. *New York Times*, 29.
- Parnas, D. L., van Schouwen, J., & Kwan, S. P. (1990). Evaluation of safety-critical software. *Communications of the ACM*, 33, 636-648.
- Pollack, A. (1991, January 1). Transforming the Decade: 10 Critical Technologies; Software Writing From an Art To a Science. *New York Times*, 39.

- Redmond, L. (1998, May 11). The return of a living legend: Lucille Redmond talks to Bob Bemer, program pioneer and the man riding to the world's rescue with plans to put a 'silver bullet' into the Year 2000 problem. *Irish Times*, 12.
- Regan, M. B. (1998, December 20). Ticking down to the millennium bug. *Atlanta Journal and Constitution*, 1R.
- Richards, E. (1990, December 10). Writing software: A quirky, labor-intensive scramble. *Washington Post*, A1.
- Shahin, M. (1999, December 27). The bug that ate the world. *Ottawa Citizen*, A1.
- Srader, D. W. (2003). *The Nuremberg doctors' trial: Framing collective memory through argument*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, University of Georgia, Athens.
- Srader, D. W. (2005, November). *Medical claims, death warrants and polling data: the Fletcher model*. Paper presented at the annual meeting of the National Communication Association, Boston.
- Srader, D. W. (2006, November). *Interpreting the debate, debating the interpretation: Breyer and Scalia on comparative constitutional law*. Paper presented at the annual meeting of the National Communication Association, San Antonio.
- Waters, R. (2007, February 14). Software glitch hits digital gadgets. *Financial Times*, 17.
- Weingarten, G. (1999, July 18). The millenniumbug. *Washington Post*, F1.
- White, J., & Simons, B. (2002). ACM's position on the licensing of software engineers. *Communications of the ACM*, 45, 91.